

Nexus between Anthropometric Indices in Hypertensive and Normotensive Adults: A Gender-Based Study in a Sprawling Urban Community

Norbert Sunday Chukwu

Faculty of Postgraduate Studies, Texila American University, Georgetown, Guyana

Aloysius Obinna Ikwuka

College of Medicine and Health Sciences, American International University West Africa, Banjul, The Gambia

Francis Chigozie Udeh

College of Medicine and Health Sciences, American International University West Africa, Banjul, The Gambia

Abstract

Adipose tissue in the body can be easily assessed using anthropometric measurements such as hip, waist, chest, and neck circumferences, waist-to-height ratio, body mass index (BMI), and subscapular skinfold thickness. Gender, age, lifestyle, ethnicity, genetics, and nutrition influence these measurements. Although extensive research exists on anthropometry, there is still a lack of data on the gender-specific correlations between anthropometric indices (or parameters), obesity, and blood pressure. This study aimed to investigate the gender differences in anthropometric parameters in hypertensive and normotensive adults, and to assess the gender-based correlations between anthropometry and blood pressure. A cross-sectional, quantitative study involving 355 adults, aged 20-75 years was conducted in Enugu City, South-East Nigeria. Data were collected using well-structured questionnaires, an electronic weighing scale, a stadiometer, a non-elastic fiber-glass tape, and an Accoson™ Desktop mercury sphygmomanometer. Student's *t*-test was used to compare anthropometric parameters, and Pearson correlation coefficient (*r*) was used to analyze the relationships between anthropometric parameters and blood pressure. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The study found a 38.0% prevalence of hypertension. Gender comparisons revealed that more males were underweight (39.0%), with no cases of class 3 obesity. Females had higher rates of overweight (27.9%) and obesity (41.3%). In the hypertensive participants, all anthropometric parameters were higher when compared to normotensive participants, except for height in males, neck circumference and subscapular-triceps ratio in females. Hypertensive and normotensive males had greater weight, height, neck and chest circumferences, waist-to-hip ratio, and subscapular-triceps ratio than their female counterparts. Conversely, hypertensive and normotensive females had greater waist circumference, hip circumference, subscapular skinfold, triceps skinfold, BMI, and waist-to-height ratio compared to males. Anthropometric parameters are key indicators of obesity, a major global health issue due to its association with hypertension. The rising trend in obesity, driven by dietary changes, disproportionately affects women. Urgent interventions are needed to promote routine exercise, particularly among administrative workers, and to raise public awareness about the benefits of physical activity.

More Information

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Introduction

Human body shape varies slightly, but factors such as age, gender, fat distribution, hormone levels, occupation, diet, socio-economic status, health, and lifestyle can significantly widen this variation [45]. The skeletal structure frames the body, while muscles and fat define its shape [45]. Fat cells, or adipocytes, form adipose tissue, which is concentrated in areas like the anterior abdominal wall, buttocks, thighs, and hips. Subcutaneous fat deposits are influenced by the same factors that affect body shape, with estrogen particularly promoting fat storage in the buttocks, thighs, and hips in women [42].

Male and female bodies differ in weight, organ dimensions, and surface measurements such as height, mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC), triceps skinfold thickness (TSF), subscapular skinfold, and circumferences of the head, chest, waist, and hips [10]. The main factor driving these differences is subcutaneous fat, which is influenced by various factors mentioned earlier. Excessive fat deposition in the hypodermis contributes to obesity, while internal fat accumulation in organs leads to health issues like atherosclerosis, hypertension, high cholesterol, and type 2 diabetes mellitus [11].

Anthropometric indices are related to different metabolic disorders. Metabolic disorders e.g. Hypertension, Adiposity, Diabetes mellitus and Dyslipidemia collectively known as Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs) are interrelated diseases and have very high morbidity and mortality rates [13, 14, 16, 31, 33, 50]. Findings from different researches have shown that hypertension, adiposity, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, asymptomatic hyperuricemia, activation of systemic immune inflammatory processes, and fibrogenesis can lead to kidney damage [17, 18, 21, 22, 23, 28, 30, 32, 51, 52, 53, 54, 58].

A cost-effective and widely accepted method for assessing body shape and subcutaneous fat is anthropometric measurement [5]. This involves using tools like inelastic tape, weighing scales, and stadiometers to take precise body measurements [43]. Two measurements could be mathematically calculated to give an index or ratio. Anthropometric data can help predict gender, obesity, hypertension, or malnutrition by assessing fat distribution, which is influenced by various factors.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), obesity and overweight are defined as excessive fat accumulation that harms health [60]. Obesity is a key link between anthropometry and hypertension. In addition to anthropometric measurements, other obesity-related indices include the Conicity Index (CI) for central obesity or abdominal fat, Body Adiposity Index (BAI), waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), and Body Mass

Index (BMI) [6, 37]. In 2022, 16% of adults (890 million people) were obese, with global obesity rates doubling since 1990 and quadrupling among adolescents [60].

High systolic blood pressure is a leading cause of disease globally, affecting both men and women [44]. In Sub-Saharan Africa, hypertension has become a significant public health issue [1, 35]. The WHO reported in 2023 that the prevalence of hypertension is steadily rising, affecting around 1.28 billion people aged 30-79, mostly in low- and middle-income countries [59]. In Nigeria, a national survey found that 38.1% of adults are hypertensive [39].

Newer and effective treatment options in patients with Metabolic Syndrome Diseases include the use of Sodium-Glucose Linked Transporter 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors e.g. Dapagliflozin, and Glucagon-like Peptide 1 Receptor Agonists (GLP-1 RAs) e.g. Liraglutide. These classes of drugs have been found to improve the efficacy of treatment and clinical course of type 2 diabetes mellitus and hypertension in patients with such comorbidities [15, 19, 20, 24, 29, 34, 55, 56, 57].

While obesity is known to increase the risk of hypertension, gender-based studies on this relationship are limited. This present study therefore aimed to investigate a gender-specific analysis of the relationships between obesity and blood pressure in an adult population using anthropometric parameters.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted at Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTH), Parklane, Enugu City, South-East Nigeria. Enugu City is a historic city known for its huge coal deposits and mines. Enugu City is also the capital city of Enugu State and is the commercial hub of the state. Enugu City has three local government areas. Enugu State with a total land area of 556 km² has 3 senatorial zones in the upper legislative arm of Nigeria which is the Nigerian Senate.

Study Design

A descriptive, cross-sectional approach was used in this study. Participants were randomly selected among the patients who visited ESUTH between September to November 2023. The methods used in the determination of anthropometry are described in the data collection sub-section.

Study Population

ESUTH is a tertiary healthcare facility that receives more than 10,000 healthcare seekers every quarter of the year. This represents the study population.

Sample Size

Similar to the study of [49], the Cochran formula was used to calculate the sample size.

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

n = sample size when the study population is >10,000;
 z = standard normal deviate = 1.96 (and corresponds to 95% confidence level);

p = prevalence of hypertension from a previous study = 35.3% [the average from two previous studies in Nigeria [3, 7];

$q = (1-p) = 1 - 0.353 = 0.647$

d = the precision set at 5% ($p < 0.05$)

Therefore, $n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.353 \times 0.647}{0.05^2} = 350.95 \sim 351$

Sample size = 351 participants. A total of 386 participants were anticipated for the study after the addition of 10% attrition rate.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Participants must reside in Enugu City	Residents outside Enugu City
Must consent to participate with no motive of financial benefit	Pregnant women
Must be between 20-75 years old	Physically impaired whose physique has a great chance to alter the results of this study
Must possess basic education	Patients using psychotropic drugs and those with renal disease confirmed either by self-reporting or medical confirmation

Study Instruments

The participant’s socio-demographic characteristics, past social, medical and family history data, blood pressure, and anthropometric measurements were recorded in well-structured questionnaires. An electronic weighing scale for measuring weight, a stadiometer for measuring height, a fibre-glass inelastic tape for the measurement of circumferences, a Holtian skinfold calliper for the selected skinfolds measurements, and Accoson™ Desktop mercury sphygmomanometer for measuring the blood pressure (BP) of study participants.

Data Collection

Eight anthropometric measurements were taken from each participant: weight to the nearest 0.1 kg; height to the nearest 0.1 cm; waist circumference (WC), head circumference (HC), neck circumference (NC), and chest circumference (CC) to the nearest 0.1 cm; and subscapular skinfold (SSF) and triceps fold (TF) to the nearest 0.1 mm.

Four other anthropometric parameters were calculated from the eight measured parameters: Body Mass Index, $BMI = \text{weight (kg)} / \text{height}^2 (\text{m}^2)$; waist-hip ratio, $WHR = \text{waist circumference (cm)} / \text{hip circumference (cm)}$;

waist-height ratio, $WHtR = \text{waist circumference (cm)} / \text{height circumference (cm)}$; and subscapular-triceps ratio (STR) = subscapular skinfold (mm) / triceps fold (mm).

- Height: Every participant removed every wig, jewelry, and shoes. While on the stadiometer platform, the back leaned against the backboard and the head aligned in Frankfurt’s horizontal plane. The stadiometer’s headpiece was pressed against the hair to take the reading.

- Weight: In addition to wigs, jewelry, shoes, and extra clothings except underwear were removed. Participants stood in an anatomical position on the weighing scale to measure their weight.

- WC: In an upright position with the shirt/blouse raised, the measuring tape was wound around the waist to take the circumference.

- HC, CC, NC: The fiber-glass measuring tape was not too loosened or tight when measuring. HC was taken at the plane where the buttock is widest; CC at the upper half of the chest; NC at the level of cervical vertebrae 4 (C4) or below the laryngeal prominence (in men).

- Skinfolds: The participants stood at ease while measuring the subscapular skinfold and triceps fold. A thickness of skinfold was pinched on the right scapular and the midpoint of the posterior arm respectively. The caliper’s jaws were applied 2cm above the two fingers and 2cm laterally (for the subscapular skinfold).

- BP: The participants sat comfortably for 5-10 minutes. Three consecutive measurements of 4-5 minutes apart were taken. At 2-3 cm above the cubital fossa of the dominant arm, an adult cuff was wrapped. The radial artery in the wrist was palpated as the cuff was inflated until the pulse disappeared. The stethoscope’s bell was placed over the brachial artery in the cubital fossa as the cuff was gently deflated. The sound change was observed with the stethoscope; the first sound indicated the systolic blood pressure and its total disappearance indicated the diastolic blood pressure. The average of the 2nd and 3rd measurements was recorded to the nearest 2mmHg.

Data Analysis

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 was used for data analysis. The socio-demographic characteristics, anthropometric parameters, and blood pressure were reported in mean values and standard deviation (SD). Student’s *t*-test was used for mean values comparison, Pearson correlation coefficient (*r*) was used to evaluate the relationships between anthropometric parameters and blood pressure, and logistic regression was used to analyze the association between anthropometric parameters and hypertension. All tests of significance were two-tailed and the level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

Participation in this study was voluntary, with the ethical clearance and permission to conduct this study obtained from the Ethics Committee of Enugu State University Teaching Hospital (ESUTH), Parklane, Enugu City. The names of study participants were not recorded. Study participants filled the consent form and consented to partake in this study without any financial inducements. A proper explanation of the study was given to every participant and every data obtained from them was held confidential. The study participants retained full autonomy throughout the study and had the unequivocal right to withdraw within two weeks of taking part in the study without any explanation or consequence.

Results

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

Parameters	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	154	43.4
Female	201	56.6
Age group (years)		
20 – 24	32	9.0
25 – 29	38	10.7
30 – 34	54	15.2
35 – 39	53	14.9
40 – 44	40	11.3
45 – 49	40	11.3
≥50	98	27.6
Marital status		
Single	93	26.2
Married	231	65.1
Divorced	3	0.8
Widow/widower	28	7.9
Occupation		
Administrative	126	35.5
Skilled labour	98	27.6
Unskilled labour	4	1.1
Unemployed	20	5.6
Pensioner	15	4.2
Others	92	25.9
Level of education		
Primary	40	11.3
Secondary	72	20.3
Tertiary	243	68.5
Level of physical activity		
Trekking	239	67.3
Riding of bicycle	10	2.8
Always using vehicle	101	28.5
Involvement in exercise	5	1.4

This study involved 355 participants, 43.4% male and 56.6% female. Among the study participants, 9.0% were aged 20-24 years, 10.7% were 25-29 years, 15.2% were 30-34 years, 14.9% were 35-39 years, 11.3% were between 40-44 years, another 11.3% were 45-49 years, and 27.6% were aged 50 years or older.

Regarding marital status, 26.2% were single, while the majority (65.1%) were married. In terms of occupation, 35.5% were administrative employees, 27.6% were skilled workers, 1.1% were unskilled workers, 5.6% were unemployed, 4.2% were retired, and 25.9% were employed in various other jobs.

Educationally, 11.3% had only primary education, 20.3% had only secondary education, and 68.5% had completed tertiary education. As for physical activity, 67.3% of the participants walked regularly, 2.8% rode bicycles, 28.5% always drove regardless of the distance, and 1.4% engaged in exercise.

Table 3: Social History of the Study Participants

Lifestyle	n	%
Patronize fast-food vendors		
Yes	213	60.0
No	142	40.0
Use of alcohol		
Yes	173	48.7
No	182	51.3
Cigarette		
Yes	27	7.6
No	328	92.4
Use of snuff		
Yes	17	4.8
No	338	95.2

Table 3 indicates that 60.0% of the participants frequently buy food from fast-food vendors and 48.7% consume alcohol. The majority of participants do not use tobacco, 92.4% do not smoke cigarettes and 95.2% do not use snuff. However, 7.6% of the participants are cigarette smokers, and 4.8% use snuff.

Table 4: Medical History of the Study Participants

Disease	Medical history	On medication
	n (%)	n (%)
Hypertension	135 (38.0)	83 (23.4)
Diab. mellitus	29 (8.2)	25 (7.0)
Stroke	6 (1.7)	6 (1.7)
Heart attack	9 (2.5)	6 (1.7)

Table 4 shows that 8.2% of the participants had diabetes mellitus, with nearly all of them taking medication. Approximately 38.0% were hypertensive, and 23.4% were on medication. All 1.7% of the participants who had experienced a transient stroke

were on medication. Additionally, 2.5% has had a heart attack, and 1.7% of them were on medication.

Stroke	49	13.8
Diabetes mellitus	72	20.3

Table 5: Family History of the Study Participants

Disease condition	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Obesity	152	42.8
Hypertension	119	33.5

Table 5 reveals that 42.8% of the participants had a family history of obesity, 33.5% had a family history of hypertension, 13.8% had a family history of stroke, and 20.3% had a family history of diabetes mellitus.

Table 6: BMI of the Study Participants

BMI (kg/m ²)	Males		Females		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Normal	3	1.9	8	4.0	11	3.1
Underweight	60	39.0	54	26.9	114	32.1
Overweight	53	34.4	56	27.9	109	30.7
Class 1 Obesity	29	18.8	51	25.4	80	22.5
Class 2 Obesity	9	5.8	23	11.4	32	9.0
Class 3 Obesity	-	-	09	4.5	09	2.5

Table 6 indicates that just a fraction (3.1%) of the participants had a normal BMI, and almost one-third (32.1%) were underweight out of which males were slightly more. Overweight in both genders was almost

equally distributed. Eighty-three females were obese while only thirty-eight males were obese, with no male in class 3 obesity.

Table 7: Comparison of Mean Anthropometric Parameters in Hypertensive and Normotensive Male Participants

Anthropometric parameters (scale)	Hypertension		t	p-value
	Yes Mean ± SD	No Mean ± SD		
Weight (kg)	85.37 ± 17.09	76.90 ± 12.54	3.545	0.001
Height (m)	1.72 ± 0.09	1.74 ± 0.08	0.983	0.327
WC (cm)	97.69 ± 13.14	89.09 ± 9.48	4.715	< 0.001
HC (cm)	105.04 ± 0.49	97.9 ± 0.45	4.269	< 0.001
NC (cm)	39.55 ± 3.62	39.05 ± 8.87	0.415	0.678
CC (cm)	105.03 ± 11.68	98.24 ± 8.08	4.003	< 0.001
SSF (mm)	25.81 ± 10.64	22.72 ± 9.69	3.671	< 0.001
TF (mm)	14.28 ± 8.67	10.67 ± 6.38	2.973	0.003
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.86 ± 5.47	25.40 ± 4.29	4.096	< 0.001
WHR	0.93 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.08	1.681	0.095
WHtR	56.85 ± 7.98	51.37 ± 5.81	4.919	< 0.001
STR	1.57 ± 0.46	1.56 ± 0.57	0.109	0.913

Note: $p < 0.05$ = statistical significant relationship; $p \geq 0.05$ = no statistical significant relationship

Table 7 revealed that weight, WC, HC, CC, SSF, TF, BMI, and WHtR were significantly higher in hypertensive male participants than in normotensive male participants ($p < 0.05$) whereas height, NC, WHR, and STR were not. The most statistical significant

anthropometric parameter was WHtR ($t=4.919$; $p < 0.001$), followed by WC ($t=4.715$; $p < 0.001$), and HC ($t=4.269$; $p < 0.001$). The least statistical significant anthropometric parameter was TF ($t=2.973$, $p=0.003$).

Table 8: Comparison of Mean Anthropometric Parameters in Hypertensive and Normotensive Female Participants

Anthropometric parameters (scale)	Hypertension		t	p-value
	Yes Mean ± SD	No Mean ± SD		
Weight (kg)	82.25 ± 18.87	76.32 ± 15.32	2.423	0.016

Height (m)	1.66 ± 0.11	1.65 ± 0.09	0.187	0.852
WC (cm)	101.44 ± 12.22	93.14 ± 12.05	4.672	< 0.001
HC (cm)	111.63 ± 12.75	104.13 ± 12.17	4.127	< 0.001
NC (cm)	35.73 ± 3.96	35.79 ± 10.32	0.050	0.960
CC (cm)	102.92 ± 14.43	95.67 ± 13.88	3.508	0.001
SSF (mm)	29.05 ± 10.42	23.73 ± 10.22	3.524	0.001
TF (mm)	24.51 ± 9.85	19.79 ± 8.09	3.662	< 0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.86 ± 6.84	28.03 ± 5.80	2.341	0.020
WHR	0.91 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.07	1.410	0.160
WHtR	61.54 ± 8.28	56.54 ± 7.91	4.236	< 0.001
STR	1.28 ± 0.44	1.48 ± 0.82	0.905	0.367

Note: $p < 0.05$ = statistical significant relationship; $p \geq 0.05$ = no statistical significant relationship

Table 8 showed that weight, WC, HC, CC, SSF, TF, BMI, and WHtR were significantly higher in hypertensive female participants than in normotensive female participants, whereas height, NC, WHR, and STR were not ($p < 0.05$). The most statistical significant

anthropometric parameter was WC ($t=4.672$; $p < 0.001$), followed by WHtR ($t=4.236$; $p < 0.001$), and HC ($t=4.127$; $p < 0.001$). The anthropometric parameter with the least differentiating strength between hypertensive and normotensive females was NC ($t=0.050$; $p=0.960$).

Table 9: Gender-Based Relationships between Anthropometric Parameters and Blood Pressure

Variables	Statistics	Male		Female	
		SBP	DBP	SBP	DBP
Weight (kg)	r	0.231	0.304	0.319	0.326
	p-value	0.004	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Height (m)	r	-0.157	0.029	0.062	0.064
	p-value	0.052	0.721	0.383	0.36
WC (cm)	r	0.365	0.339	0.408	0.421
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
HC (cm)	r	0.302	0.326	0.364	0.366
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
NC (cm)	r	0.093	0.076	-0.005	-0.027
	p-value	0.250	0.346	0.942	0.708
CC (cm)	r	0.263	0.362	0.319	0.427
	p-value	0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
SSF (mm)	r	0.358	0.284	0.324	0.355
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
TF (mm)	r	0.365	0.260	0.267	0.250
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	r	0.313	0.287	0.271	0.282
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
WHR	r	0.167	0.105	0.121	0.132
	p-value	0.038	0.193	0.087	0.062
WHtR	r	0.407	0.313	0.349	0.361
	p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
STR	r	-0.048	-0.003	-0.002	0.003
	p-value	0.551	0.972	0.973	0.967

Note: SBP = Systolic blood pressure; DPB = Diastolic blood pressure; r = Pearson correlation coefficient (-1 = negative linear correlation, 0 = no linear correlation, +1 = positive linear correlation); $p < 0.05$ = statistical significant relationship; $p \geq 0.05$ = no statistical significant relationship

Table 9 revealed that Pearson correlation coefficient (r) showed a weak positive linear correlation ($r > 0, \leq 1$;

$p < 0.05$) between anthropometric parameters and blood pressure, except for the following

anthropometric parameters: height in both genders (males had a non-significant negative and positive linear correlations for SBP and DBP respectively ($r = -0.157$ SBP, 0.029 DBP, $p > 0.05$) and women had a non-significant positive linear correlation ($r > 0$, < 1 ; $p > 0.05$). NC for both gender was [men ($r > 0$, < 1 ; $p > 0.05$) and women ($r < 0$; $p > 0.05$)], WHR for both gender was [men ($r > 0$, < 1 ; $p > 0.05$) and women ($r > 0$, < 1 ; $p > 0.05$)]; STR for both gender was [men ($r < 0$; $p > 0.05$) and women ($r = -0.002$ SBP, 0.003 DBP, $p > 0.05$)]. NC, WHR, and STR were not significantly related to blood pressure.

The anthropometric parameter that best correlated significantly with blood pressure in both men and women was WC [men ($r = 0.365$ SBP, 0.339 DBP, $p < 0.001$) and women ($r = 0.408$ SBP, 0.421 DBP, $p < 0.001$)]. HC, CC, SSF, and WHtR also had a statistical significant relationship with blood pressure in both genders ($p < 0.001$). The relationship between WHtR and SBP was greater in men ($r = 0.407$) than in women ($r = 0.349$). Conversely, the relationship between WHtR and DBP was greater in women ($r = 0.361$) than in men ($r = 0.313$).

Table 10: Correlations between BMI, WC, and Hypertension in Male Participants

Parameters	Hypertension		p-value	OR	95% C.I. for OR
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)			
BMI (kg/m²)					
Normal	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)			
Underweight	20 (33.3)	40 (66.7)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Overweight	18 (34.0)	35 (66.0)	0.944	1.029	0.471 – 2.248
Class 1 Obesity	16 (55.2)	13 (44.8)	0.052	2.462	0.993 – 6.100
Class 2 Obesity	8 (88.9)	1 (11.1)	0.011	16.00	1.869 – 136.951
WC (cm)					
Obese	38 (60.3)	25 (39.7)	< 0.001	4.243	2.134 – 8.436
Normal	24 (26.4)	67 (73.6)			

Note: N/A = Not Applicable

Using logistic regression, Table 10 showed that male participants with class 2 obesity were 16 times more likely to be hypertensive, whereas male participants

with obese spectrum of WC were 4 times more likely to be hypertensive compared to male participants without obesity.

Table 11: Correlations between BMI, WC, and Hypertension in Female Participants

Parameters	Hypertension		p-value	OR	95% C.I. for OR
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)			
BMI (kg/m²)					
Normal	2 (25.0)	6 (75.0)			
Underweight	17 (31.5)	37 (68.5)	0.711	0.725	0.133 – 3.972
Overweight	16 (28.6)	40 (71.4)	0.739	0.871	0.385 – 1.969
Class 1 Obesity	20 (39.2)	31 (60.8)	0.408	1.404	0.629 – 3.136
Class 2 Obesity	12 (52.2)	11 (47.8)	0.090	2.374	0.874 – 6.451
Class 3 Obesity	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	0.035	4.353	0.971 – 19.512
WC (cm)					
Obese	69 (39.2)	107 (60.8)	0.031	3.386	1.114 – 10.286
Normal	4 (16.0)	21 (84.0)			

Using logistic regression, Table 11 showed that class 3 obesity and obese spectrum of WC were significantly associated with hypertension ($p < 0.05$), and that class 3 obesity (4.4 times) and obese spectrum of WC (3.4 times) were more likely to cause hypertension in females compared to normal females.

Discussion

Anthropometry which is the measurement of the human body, has been practised since the dawn of

humanity and plays a vital role in various fields such as health, engineering, art, and commerce. In healthcare, it is an affordable tool for assessing nutritional status [10]. BMI which is an anthropometric parameter helps in determining obesity. Obesity is a known risk factor for hypertension. Obesity is also a risk factor for Non-Hodgkin lymphoma [25].

The global shift from healthy, vegetable-based diets to high-calorie, processed foods is raising concerns due to

the increased risk of health issues like hypertension, heart disease, obesity, and cancer, especially among alcohol and tobacco users with low physical activity levels. High-calorie, processed food increases oxidative stress. Increased oxidative stress can lead to mutation which is an alteration in the DNA sequence which produces new alleles [27]. The induction of oxidative stress is linked to major free radicals. Among these major free radicals, superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, and hydroperoxyl radical are of physiological significance. Non-radical of physiological significance is hydrogen peroxide [4, 26, 46].

In this present study, fast food and alcohol consumption were prevalent social factors, with 38.0% prevalence rate of hypertension among the study participants. This agrees with findings of the following reports: 27% reported by the World Health Organization [59], 38.1% reported by Odili, *et al* [39], and within the 2.1-47.2% range reported by Akinlua, *et al* [3]. In addition, 42.8% of the study participants had a family history of obesity, and 33.5% had a family history of hypertension, indicating that genetic predispositions, along with poor diet (cholesterol- and fat-based), alcohol consumption, and tobacco use [47, 48] may contribute to obesity and hypertension [9, 12, 40].

Using BMI to assess general obesity, this present study found that 39.0% of males were underweight, no males were in class 3 obesity. 27.9% of females were overweight and 41.3% females were obese. These findings are consistent with a national data which reported the prevalence of obesity for men and women as 12.9% and 19.8% respectively [2], and the Global Nutrition Report where 11% adult males and 2% adult females in Nigeria were underweight, 24% adult males and 39% adult females were overweight, and 6% adult males and 16% adult females were obese [8]. The Global Nutrition Report further stated that the prevalence of overweight and obesity among Nigerian adults is currently increasing [8]. Higher estrogen levels in women are likely responsible for their greater fat accumulation in areas such as the hips and thighs [42], with fat serving as an energy reserve during pregnancy [38].

All anthropometric indices were higher in hypertensive male participants than in normotensive male participants, except for height which was insignificantly lower. In females, all anthropometric indices were higher in the hypertensive cohorts than in the normotensives, except for NC, and STR which were insignificantly lower. These findings align with previous studies in Korea [36] and in Nigeria [41], and the explanation for the higher anthropometric indices in hypertensive males and females is that 60.0% of the participants in this present study eat high-calorie and high-cholesterol fast food, which together with alcohol

consumption, and other risk factors can cause overweight and obesity just as seen in hypertensive participants.

Gender comparisons show that hypertensive and normotensive males had higher weight, height, NC, CC, WHR, and STR than their female counterparts. Conversely, hypertensive and normotensive females had higher WC, HC, SSF, TF, BMI, and WHtR than their male counterparts. The higher WC and HC in females support observations on fat distribution in women's waist, buttocks, and thigh [42].

Pearson correlation analysis showed a weak but significant relationship between blood pressure and anthropometric indices such as weight, WC, HC, CC, SSF, TF, BMI, and WHtR ($r=0.105-0.427$, $p<0.05$) for both genders, indicating that as obesity worsens, the risk of hypertension increases, supporting the fact that obesity is a risk factor for hypertension. The Pearson correlation analysis in this present study supports the results of another anthropometric study conducted in a Korean population [36].

Nevertheless, some of the limitations of this present study include the fact that other causes of hypertension e.g. renal disease, aortic and renal artery stenosis, and pheochromocytoma were not investigated. Bias in this present study could be from selection, information received, and measurements even though extreme case sampling, well structured self-administered questionnaire, participants with basic education, and standardized equipments were used.

Conclusion

Although subcutaneous fat functions as insulation and energy storage, however it significantly impacts anthropometric indices, and poses health risks. Adult males are more likely to be underweight, whereas adult females are more likely to be overweight or obese regardless of their blood pressure status. With 38.0% prevalence rate of hypertension, most anthropometric indices are higher in hypertensives except for height, NC, and STR. Obesity, together with diet, genetics, medical conditions, and lifestyle factors such as alcohol consumption and tobacco use, increases the risk of hypertension.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest. This manuscript was written from an original, self-funded, research work and has not been published

earlier neither is it under consideration for publication elsewhere.

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